

CEU

*Universidad
Cardenal Herrera*

CoARA

Action Plan

2024-2027

Office of the Vice-Rector for Research and Knowledge Transfer

July 2025

1. INTRODUCTION

The Universidad CEU Cardenal Herrera is a public-service oriented and privately-managed university that forms part of the Fundación San Pablo CEU, Spain's largest privately-run educational institution. Our educational approach is rooted in the principles of Christian humanism – principles that drive our social commitment. This is reflected in our extensive scholarship programmes and pioneering initiatives in student volunteering and community service, both nationally and internationally. Our values also the platform for our research efforts. Our research seeks to improve the society we live in, from both the technical and humanistic perspectives.

The Universidad CEU Cardenal Herrera has been part of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) since 26 April 2023, when the University also signed up to the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA).

As signatories to the Agreement, we are committed to drawing up an Action Plan, which, subject to its approval by the Governing Council, is to be implemented during the period 2024-27.

COMMITMENT	SCOPE	ACTION	TIME PERIOD
1. Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.	Broaden the spectrum of what is valued in research, while acknowledging that this may vary across disciplines and that each individual researcher should not be expected to contribute to all activities at once.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review the institutional policy regarding research assessment. - Develop a responsible research policy that takes into account the diversity of research areas, the different levels of research careers, leadership within research groups, the diversity of the means of disseminating research results, as well as the researcher's contribution. (Use of the CRediT taxonomy). 	2024-2027
2. Base research assessment on qualitative evaluation supported by quantitative indicators.	Assessment should rely on qualitative judgement for which peer review is central, supported by responsibly used quantitative indicators where appropriate.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise awareness about the responsible use of metrics. - Raise awareness about the progress of reform in research assessment (Open Science /Social Impact). 	2024-2027
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and the h-index.	<p>Abandon the inappropriate use of journal- and publication-based metrics in research assessment.</p> <p>Inappropriate uses include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - relying exclusively on author-based metrics (for example, counting papers, patents, citations, grants, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stop considering the JIF and h-index as necessary or sufficient indicators for assessing research quality. - Assessors should not base their decisions solely on these bibliometric indicators. 	2024-2027

	<p>etc.) to assess quality and/or impact.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - assessing outputs based on metrics related to publication venue, format or language. - relying on any other metric that does not adequately capture quality and/or impact. 		
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organizations in research assessment.	Acknowledge the methodological limitations of such approaches and avoid the trickle-down effects on research and research assessment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recognize the limitations of the criteria used in compiling rankings. - Review their use in research assessment (e.g. internal competitive funding processes). 	2024-2027
5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organizational changes committed to	Provide resources to enable the engagement of researchers at all career stages in reforming research assessment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preparation of the Action Plan. - Creation of a committee for the implementation and monitoring of the Action Plan. - Annual budget allocation for the implementation of the Action Plan activities. 	2024-2027
6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes	Research assessment by research funders should consider disciplinary, multi-, inter-, and trans-disciplinary research as well as contributions to knowledge generation and scientific, technological, economic, cultural and societal impact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review and update internal competitive funding processes (criteria, documents, etc.). - Develop a code of practice that incorporates the principles of responsible research. 	2024-2027

<p>7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.</p>	<p>Pay particular attention to raising awareness among researchers at all career stages.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training activities related to CoARA principles. - Internal communication activities. - Training activities related to research assessment (<i>sexenios</i> [six-year assessment periods], accreditations, AIE, etc.). - Develop how-to guides (competitive funding processes, etc.) - Opportunities to discuss the CoARA principles and their implementation at CEU UCH. - Review online resources and materials to ensure that content is relevant and easy to find. 	<p>2024-2027</p>
<p>8. Exchange practices and experiences that enable mutual learning within and beyond CoARA.</p>	<p>Contribute to the development of guidance and common approaches in order to minimize contradictions or incompatibilities between the assessment practices used by different organizations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participate in open forums: CoARA, National Chapter, etc. - Share materials and best practices with the CoARA community. 	<p>2024-2027</p>
<p>9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the commitments</p>	<p>Monitoring and updating on progress in fulfilling the commitments made.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publication of the Action Plan (Zenodo). - Internal communication regarding the gradual implementation of the commitments made. 	<p>2024-2027</p>
<p>10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state of</p>	<p>Monitoring of successful cases of more qualitative research assessment or innovative proposals.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stay informed about progress through participation in events or other meaningful activities. 	<p>2024-2027</p>

the art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research			
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2. GOVERNANCE AND MONITORING OF THE ACTION PLAN

The actions of the UCH-CoARA Action Plan 2024-2027 fall within the institutional remit of the Office of the Vice-Rector for Research and Knowledge Transfer.

The Action Plan has been drawn up by a working group made up of researchers and technical staff from the Office of the Vice-Rector for Research and Knowledge Transfer.

The working group will assess the implementation and progress of the Action Plan every six months.

The Action Plan will be:

- Submitted for approval to the Research Committee
- Submitted for approval to the Governing Council